

THE CORRELATION OF TEACHERS' ASSESSMENT ABOUT PRINCIPAL ASSERTIVE LEADERSHIP STYLE WITH TEACHER PERFORMANCE OF SMPN 01 JASINGA BOGOR REGENCY

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the correlation of teacher's assessment of Assertive Leadership Style Principal with Teacher of SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency Performance. This research uses Quantitative method. The independent variable is assessment of assertive leadership style of principal. The dependent variable is teacher performance. The hypothesis proposed in this study is "there is a positive relationship between assertive leadership style of principal and teacher performance". This research was conducted at SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency. Sampling was done at SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency by taking all the existing population that amounted to 41 people or called the total sample. The results of this study indicate that: (1) from the calculation of product moment note that the value of r_{count} is 0.426742 while r_{table} is 0.316 with 5% significant limit means r_{count} bigger than r_{table} is 0.426742 < 0.316. (2) there is correlation between teacher's evaluation toward assertive leadership style with teacher performance, proven r_{count} (2,947) bigger than r_{tabel} (2,021), $2,947 > 2,021$ which mean H_0 is processed while H_1 is accepted.

Keywords: Teacher Assessment, Assertive Of Leadership Style, Teacher Performance

PRELIMINARY

In explaining about the leadership, there are some things that need to be considered include the power and authority that is the ability to act for a leader to move his subordinates to follow his will in achieving the predetermined goal, the authority that is the various advantages possessed by a leader so that the superiority of people Others are obedient and willing to carry out their desired activities, the ability is the overall power of both social skills and skills beyond anyone else. According to George R. Terry in Daryanto, explains that leadership is the activity of influencing others to volunteer to struggle to achieve group goals. Through these formulas can be concluded that leadership is a process whereby a person who has the science and art to influence subordinates in order to work together in achieving the goals that have been set. The characteristics and nature of leadership is a leader who controls and directs his subordinates in achieving common goals.

Education consists of various components for education as a process can take place. Components after students are educators or teachers in school. The role of teachers in school in addition to the strategic is also very decisive because the teacher is the person who holds the key in the success of the educational process that will take place. Therefore, efforts are needed to improve the human resources that enable the increase of professionalism. Law no. 14 Year 2005 in Sudarwan Danim, that teachers appointed by the government or local government can be placed in a structural position. The provisions on this matter have been

regulated by government regulations, although still required more regulations in its more operational subordinates.¹

Teacher performance is the most decisive factor of learner quality. Thus, improving the quality of teacher quality education needs to get major attention in setting policy. Performance quality is influenced by some very complex factors and indicates whether professional coaching and development in a job can succeed or fail. Factors that affect the performance, namely: (1) Individual variables, including ability, skill, physical mental, family background, social, (2) level, experience, demography (age, origin, gender). (3) Organization Variables, including resources, leadership, rewards, job design structures. (4) Psychological variables that include perception, attitude, personality, learning and motivation.

The performance of teachers is very important to be considered and evaluated because teachers carry professional duties means that tasks can only be done with special competencies gained through educational programs. Teachers have responsibilities that can be broadly classified as follows: (1). Teachers as teachers, (2). Teachers as mentors and (3). Teacher as the class administrator.

According Mangkunegara in Jerry H. Makawimbang states that the factors that affect the performance include: 1) Psychic ability factors ability employees consist of potential ability (IQ) and ability of reality (education). 2) Motivation factors formed from the attitude (attitude) of an employee in the situation (situation) work. Motivation is a condition that moves self directed employees to achieve the goals of work. Mental attitude is a mental condition that encourages a person to try to achieve maximum job potential.²

A person's performance can be improved if there is a correspondence between the job and his or her skills, as well as the teacher's placement in the field of duty. Placing teachers according to their skills is absolutely necessary. When teachers are given tasks not in accordance with their skills will result in decreased work and results of their work, will also cause a sense of dissatisfaction in themselves. Feeling disappointed will hamper the moral development of teachers work. The formation of conducive iklim on the work situation becomes a supporting factor for the improvement of performance, because the comfort in working to make the teacher think calmly and concentrate only on the task that is being implemented. Leadership-oriented style of organizational members exercising their leadership seeks to encourage, guide and guide empathetically and provide trust to members to carry out a work with their own work.

In a formal institution or organization, both small and large can be found a leader without exception, including the educational institutions. In educational institutions, especially primary and secondary schools, people who lead or become leaders known as the principal. The leader is one of the most important elements in an institution or organization. The advancement of an organization is largely determined by the leader's ability to manage his organization.

The principal is a functional teacher who is given the task to lead a school where the learning process is organized, or where there is an interaction between the teacher giving the

¹ Sudarman Danim, 2010. *Kepemimpinan Pendidikan*. Bandung: Alfabeta, h. 178

² Ibid., h.219-220

lesson and the student receiving the lesson.³ Thus for the purpose of school can be achieved, then the principal in carrying out his duties and functions requires a style in the lead, which is known by the leadership style of the principal.

This opinion describes things that can affect a person's performance, individual factors with their unique psychological characteristics and organizational factors interact in a process that can realize a quality performance performed by a person in carrying out its role and duties within the organization.

The low performance of teachers will affect the implementation of tasks that in turn will also affect the achievement of educational goals. Low teacher performance should be identified cause. There are various factors that can affect the performance of a teacher. In this condition, the principal plays an important role, because it can provide an enabling environment for teachers to work with passion. With the supervision skills it has, the principal builds and maintains a positive teacher performance.

Leadership comes from the word lead that contains the sense of directing, organizing, influencing or motivating. According to Sanusi in Jerry H. Makawimbang states that leadership is an integral part of the ability, ideals, and spirit of nationalism in organizing, controlling and managing family households and organizations or households. Overton explains leadership is the ability to gain action and through others with trust and cooperation. Fieldler says that leadership is essentially a pattern of relationships between individuals who use authority and influence on groups of people to work together to achieve goals.

Assertive leadership style is more aggressive and has a great deal of attention on personal control than other leadership styles. Assertive type leaders are more open to conflict and criticism. Decision-making emerges from the process of argumentation with multiple points of view so that a satisfactory conclusion arises.

In carrying out his duties, he would accept, even expect opinions and suggestions from his subordinates in an organization he leads. Assertive leadership always expects constructive arguments from subordinates and is accepted as a conclusion to produce a satisfactory decision. A leader who has this type of assertive leadership has trust in his subordinates that they have the ability to carry out their duties properly and are responsible for their respective jobs. This assertive leader has a great deal of attention and more openness in criticism and suggestions, with the existence of an aggregation from several points of view so that a satisfactory decision or conclusion can arise.⁴

The principal is a functional teacher who is assigned to lead a school where the learning process is organized, or where there is an interaction between the teacher giving the lesson and the student receiving the lesson. According Mulyono in Jerry H. Makawimbang, that the progress of the school will be more important if people give attention to the principal's gait for the following reasons. First, the principal is a central figure of education. Second, the school is as an educational community that needs a leader to utilize the potential that exists within the school.⁵

³ Jerry H. Makawimbang, 2013. *Kepemimpinan Pendidikan yang Bermutu*. Bandung: Alfabeta, h. 61

⁴ <http://irasaffaghira.blogspot.com/2013/05/pilihan-itu-adalah-berani-bersikap.html>

⁵ Jerry H. Makawimbang, Op. cit, h. 61-62

The style of leadership is a characteristic pattern of a leader's character when influencing his subordinates, what the leader chooses to do, the way the leader acts in influencing the members of his group to form his leadership style.⁶

The principal as a manager occupies a predetermined position within the school organization. The principal has a top position that holds the key to success in achieving the predetermined objectives, the condition indicating that the principal as a holder of services or a special field of professional services. Principal leadership is the principal way or effort in motivating, encouraging, directing influences and motivating teachers, staff, students, parents, and other related parties to work and participate in achieving the stated objectives.

In performing its duties, an assertive leader always accepts and even expects the arguments of its members. Also constructive criticisms from members are accepted as feedback and made conclusions in obtaining satisfactory decisions. He has self-confidence and trust in his members that they have the responsibility and ability to work well. An assertive leader always tries to establish communication openness. He always tried to build the spirit of its members in running and developing its performance. Besides, he also provides opportunities for the emergence of leadership skills as power and responsibility

Assertive leaders interpret their leadership not as dictators, but as leaders who are in the middle of the group members. Relationship with members of his group is not as superior to his subordinates. Assertive leaders always try to motivate their members to work cooperatively for the achievement of common goals. In his actions and efforts, he always stems from the interests and needs of his group, and accepts the arguments of his members.

From the background of the problems mentioned above, so it can encourage the authors to examine the Relationship of Teacher Assessment of Relationship Style Assertiveness Principal Principal with Teacher Performance SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency.

This study aims to determine whether or not the relationship of assertive leadership style of principal with teacher performance. With the translation as follows (1) To know the teacher's assessment of the assertive leadership style of the principal. (2) To know the performance picture of teachers SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency (3) To know the association of assertive leadership style of principal with the performance of teachers SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency?

RESEARCH METHODS

In doing research, researchers can choose what type of method will be used in conducting research. This research method is survey method with correlational form, aiming to test the hypothesis stating the existence of relationship between free variable Assessment Leadership Assertive Principal (X) with variable bound Teacher Performance (Y).

Sugiyono states that the population is a generalization region consisting of objects / subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by the researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions. In this study, the population is a teacher SMPN 01 Jasinga, amounting to approximately 41 people.

⁶ Daryanto, Op. cit, h. 103

The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by that population. To simplify the process of collecting and processing data, the author uses sampling techniques, with reference to the opinion Suharsimi Arikunto that if the subject is less than 100, then better taken all. So the research is a population study. Furthermore, if the subject is larger can be taken 10-15%, or 20-25% or more. In this study the researchers took all the existing population of teachers with a total of 41 people or called the total sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the beginning of the study, researchers collected data from two sources, namely the acquisition of assertive leadership style questionnaire and questionnaire School head teacher performance. Questionnaire compiled by the authors consists of 30 statements about the principal's leadership style (as variable X) and 30 statements to determine teacher performance (as a variable Y), which are distributed to 41 respondents. Who scores Data Range (Range), Number of Classes, Interval Length, Mode, Median, and Mean.

Based on data obtained from the variable Description of Leadership Style Principal as follows. Based on the test results of the study, obtained the lowest score 83 with a highest score of 118, a score range of data 35, score a lot of class 6, 6 interval length score, score 104.166 mode, a median score of 105.612 and 103.939 mean.

Master Performance of Data Description. Based on the test results of the study, obtained the lowest score 97 with the highest score of 119, a score range of data 22, score a lot of class 6, score interval length of 4, the score 112.944 mode, a median score of 93.62, and a mean of 84.43. The calculation of real value for each score (value) listed.

The data has been collected and if the researchers to determine the effect of the academic supervision of the school head teacher performance, then the product moment correlation calculation, that is:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Once known between the two variables above through statistical Pearson product moment, then subsequently inserted into the correlation Pearson product moment with the following description : $N = 41$, $\sum X = 4208$, $\sum Y = 4480$, $\sum XY = 460516$, $\sum X^2 = 433964$, $\sum Y^2 = 490872$, $(\sum X) = 17707264$, $(\sum Y)^2 = 20070400$. Data using correlation formula Pearson product moment then obtained = **0,426742**

Furthermore, to declare the size of the contribution of variable X to Y can be determined by the coefficient formula is reflected as follows: $KD = r_{xy}^2 \times 100\% = 18,21\%$ This means the influence of assertive leadership style of principal 18.21% and the remaining 81.79% is determined by other variables or variations that occur on teacher performance. The performance of teachers is 18.21% influenced by the assertive leadership style of the principal.

To test the significance before interpreted, then first t test on a significant level, that is :

$$t_{\text{count}} = \frac{r_{xy} \sqrt{N-2}}{\sqrt{1-r_{xy}^2}} = 2,947 \quad t_{\text{count}} \quad \text{At a significant level of 0.05 with dk} = N - 2 = 41 - 2 =$$

39 is 0,316. From the calculation results obtained t counted 2.947, while t table 2.021 which

means $t_{\text{count}} (2.947) > t_{\text{tabel}} (2.021)$ then the correlation coefficient is significant. Thus, there is a significant relationship between assertive leadership style of principal and teacher performance.

Interpretation of the data presented below refers to the problems that have been formulated in Chapter I. The problem questioned whether there is a significant relationship between assertive headmaster leadership style of teacher performance.

The results prove that the assertive leadership style of principal SMPN 01 Jasinga of Bogor Regency has a very high criteria of 48.780%, high criteria of 46.341%, and moderate criteria of 4.878%. Viewed from the average of 103,939 which included high criteria. Thus it can be concluded that the teacher's assessment of assertive leadership style of principal in SMPN 01 Jasinga belong to high criteria.

Based on the results of the research above also, that teacher performance in high criterion equal to 21,951%, and very high criterion equal to 78,049%. Viewed from the average of 109,329 which includes high criteria. Thus it can be concluded that the performance of teachers SMPN 01 Jasinga included in the high criteria.

To show whether or not there is a relationship between assertive leadership style of principal and teacher performance, then the product moment correlation test is done. Based on the test results r_{xy} arithmetic of 0.426742 and r_{xy} table at $N = 41 - 2 = 39$ and 5% significance level obtained 0.316. Afterwards, measured the size of the contribution of variable X to Y is determined by the coefficient formula is reflected with the result of 18.21%. It means that the influence of assertive leadership style of principal is 18.21% and the rest is 81.79% determined by other variables or variations that occur to the performance teacher.

Furthermore, to test its significance then do the t test. Based on t test result of 2,947 and t table with degrees of freedom ($dk = N - 2$) and $\alpha = 0.05$ of 2.021. This means that t count is greater than t_{table} 2,947 > 2,021. Test results on the correlation coefficient obtained from the calculation that r_{xy} 0.426742. Thus H_0 rejected while H_a accepted which means there is a relationship between assertive headmaster leadership style to Teacher performance in SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency. It is proved by the result of the value of r count is greater than t_{table} .

From the calculation of the moment product above is known that the value of r t_{count} is 0.426742 while r table is 0.316 with 5% significant limit means the value of r count is greater than t_{table} that is $0.426742 > 0.316$. Criteria testing, namely: Reject H_0 , If $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$, Reject H_a , if $t_{\text{count}} < t_{\text{table}}$ H_0 (null hypothesis) = To express no effect Between two variables (X and Y) H_a (Alternative hypothesis) = To state the influence Between two variables (X and Y)

Thus the value of product moment r there is a relationship between assertive headmaster leadership style on teacher performance, and t on the calculation of significant level 0.05 with $dk = N - 2 = 39$ also there is a positive relationship, proven t arithmetic (2,947) is greater than t_{table} (2.021), ie $2.947 > 2.021$ which means H_0 rejected while H_a accepted. To state and determine the weight of assertive leadership style relationship with the principal teacher performance, the authors use the criteria of magnitude coefficients quoted from reference books Sugiyono. Based on the criteria of interpretation level above, it is known that r hitung is 0.426742 which means that between 0,400 up to 0,599 it can be said

that teacher's assessment toward assertive leadership style of principal with performance of teacher of SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency has relation in medium criterion.

CONCLUSIONS IMPLICATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

Based on the results of hypothesis testing research, it can be drawn conclusions as the results of this study. The authors can conclude from the results of this study are as follows:

1. The results of the study prove that the teacher's assessment of Assertive Leadership Style of principal SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency, obtained the lowest score 83 with the highest score 118, the average score (mean) of 103.939, the median of 105.612 and mode of 104.166. The percentage of scores on teacher assessment of the principal's principal leadership style is the value below very high 48.780%, high 46.341%, and moderate 4.878%. Thus it can be concluded that the teacher's assessment of the assertive leadership style of SMPN 01 Jasinga head of Bogor Regency belong to medium criteria.
2. Based on the results of the above research also, that the performance of teachers, obtained the lowest score 97 with a score of 119, the average score (mean) of 109.329, median of 93.62 and mode of 112.944. The percentage of Teacher scores is a value below the high average of 21.951% and very high at 78.049%. Thus it can be concluded that the performance of teachers SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency included in the criteria are.
3. Based on t test results of 2.947 and t table with degrees of freedom (dk) = N-2 and $\alpha = 0.05$ of 2.021. This means t_{count} is greater than t_{table} ($2,947 > 2,021$). Test results on the correlation coefficient obtained from the calculation that r_{xy} 0.426742 significant. Thus H_0 rejected while H_a accepted which means there is a positive relationship between the teacher's assessment of assertive leadership style principal with the performance of teachers SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency. It is proved by the result of the value of r count is greater than r table.

B. Implications

Based on the results of the above research, there are several implications that can be stated that

1. Assessment of teachers toward assertive leadership style of SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency is classified in the criterion of the performance of teachers SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency is included in the criteria are as well as there is a positive relationship between the teacher's assessment of assertive leadership style headmaster with teacher performance SMPN 01 Jasinga District Bogor. So the process of teaching and learning is a process that contains a series of actions of teachers and students on the basis of reciprocal relationships that take place in educational situations to achieve certain goals. Principal leadership style is very influential on the performance of teachers in the learning process.
2. Performance of teacher or job performance is a result obtained by a teacher in carrying out the responsibilities and tasks carried to him based on skills, experience, and sincerity and time with the resulting output. Teacher performance can be seen from how far the teacher

completes her task in teaching compared to job standards. A teacher in performing his duties as an educator requires the influence of the principal's leadership, the principal leadership expected by his subordinates is the leadership that they perceive that the purpose of the educational institution is a shared responsibility so that the principal must be able to create a good working climate in order to achieve that goal .

C. Suggestions

After concluding the results of the above study, the authors want to provide advice to improve the performance of teachers SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor district, especially in carrying out the leadership of the principal in leading subordinates, as for the advice is:

1. The principal as a leader in the educational institution is expected to provide positive relationships, give attention, and create a conducive working climate for teachers in SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor so that teachers can improve its performance.
2. It is expected that the principal can maintain assertiveness in order to improve teacher performance in SMPN 01 Jasinga Bogor Regency.

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